

MARKETING TECHNIQUES USED BY POLITICAL PARTIES – A BRIEF LITERATURE SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Like products and services, political parties have to do "marketing" to grab the highest "market share," that is, the vote share. Like business firms, parties should know where they remain in their "market." Marketing isn't a movement that political parties may enjoy at their circumspection; it is a steady and vital political capacity to go to verifiably or expressly, effectively, or something else. The parties compete intensely to grab the voters' attention and convince them to vote for their Party. All this involves a good deal of "marketing." This paper briefly reviews some recent literature dealing with political parties' marketing techniques not just for winning votes once but also for building a vote bank and developing voter loyalty.

Keywords: Political parties, Marketing techniques, Voters

Introduction

ET Brand Equity (2019) has reported that as per the Centre for Media Studies estimates, an amount of Rs.50,000 crores was to be spent on the 2019 Lok Sabha elections. This amount is a rise of 40% over what was spent in the 2014 Lok Sabha elections – Rs.35,000 crores. According to the media buying agencies, expenditure on paid media by various political parties in 2019 was expected to rise to 73% compared to the 2014 Lok Sabha polls to about Rs.2,500 crore. Interesting this was to include digital advertising spend of around Rs.500 crore. These numbers are indicative of the significance attached to marketing by the political parties. What are the important marketing techniques that the political parties use? This is the research question that will be answered by this review paper based on some of the latest published research.

Review of Literature

Safiullah et al. (2017), in their paper, say that in the current period of the electronic revolution, when social media has become the methods and end of all communication, democracies are contemplating whether social media can be a substantial marker to foresee elections outcome. With the expansion in notoriety and development in social media utilization, the current examination targets looking at whether the utilization of social

media (Twitter) affected the 2014 General elections outcome. For this research, an aggregate of 8,877,275 social media buzz for 100 days from January 01, 2014, to April 09, 2014, of 12 Indian political parties has been thought of. The outcome demonstrates that social media buzz essentially affects the outcome of General elections 2014.

Perannagariand Chakrabarti (2020) in their current study presents a quantitative examination of the literature on political marketing utilizing a bibliometric approach. This study has investigated 214 records gathered from the Web of Science data set for the time frame somewhere in the range of 1996 and 2018 utilizing VOS viewer programming and bibliometrix R package. In view of the insights acquired from the examination, the authors talk about the underlying attributes of different logical specialists associated with the distribution cycle. The aftereffects of this study demonstrate that the literature on political marketing is exceptionally divided is as yet in its early stages. It further burdens the need to improve coordinated effort among researchers and advance this discipline inside the research local area.

Political parties target convincing voters, who are the vital components of target market to win political race by acquiring a higher vote potential than their rivals (Ozturk and Coban, 2019). Regardless of whether elector inclinations are formed by political

components or by the impacts of social climate has become the focal point of the investigations inside the pertinent literature. The primary reason for this study is to decide the impact of political marketing exercises and word of mouth communication and to decide mediator job WOM communication on elector practices. The study is directed in Konya on a sample comprising of 432 voters and the size of which is controlled by convenience sampling strategy by utilizing eye to eye overview technique. Political marketing, word of mouth communication and elector practices are affirmed by structural equation demonstrating through confirmatory factor analysis. Because of the study, political marketing exercises and word of mouth communication are found to positively affect citizen conduct. Besides, it is resolved that word of mouth communication have mediator job in the impact of political marketing exercises on elector practices.

This paper (Anim et al., 2019) intends to investigate the connections between political marketing by means of social media and youthful voters' political interest in Ghana. Moreover, this study looks at the mediating job political adequacy plays in improving the relationship. With a positivist outlook, and receiving the review methodology, information accumulated from the survey controlled from the sampled 320 youthful voters (18-29 years) in Greater Accra were quantitatively investigated. An exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation displaying (SEM) were utilized to evaluate and affirm the proposed scales legitimacy and the connections of the research model.

Political marketing is a subject that has acquired and more consideration, from both scholars, and the general population, because of the political changes these days, and to the expanded openness brought by the Internet and the new methods for communication (Vladimir, 2018). Social media marketing is tending to the new sections of populace, which are strongly engaged with their online life, and are hesitant to customary media, like TV and papers. As all marketers are zeroing in on being available on, and acquiring however much as could be expected from the social stages, political marketers are likewise

coordinating this into their procedures. The principal example of overcoming adversity to be credited to a great extent to the presence of social media in a mission, is the one of Barack Obama's 2008 Presidential success, a second that can be viewed as the genuine start of social media governmental issues.

At the point when a discussion is going on whether marketing ought to be widened to new territories, the current study centers on one such area, namely parts of political marketing with regards to Bangladesh (Alam and Riva, 2016). Given that each lawmaker needs to win votes in the political decision, the ideas of marketing, such as leadership, media, media campaign, special strategy, superstar underwriting, and so on can be applied to meet the voters' political requirements, and in this way making their ideal democratic goal. Following an overview of the understudies of the Faculty of Business Studies, University Dhaka, it is discovered that the political marketing factors are determinants of casting a ballot expectation, as upheld by the coefficient of various assurance, which is .686, inferring that such factors clarify 68.6% of changeability in the democratic aim. Intelligent application of political marketing may assist a ton with keeping up sound legislative issues for both the political parties and the electorate.

Digital media have a significant job in media procedures of organizations, yet they are currently an indispensable tool for every political faction (Garaj, 2018). The traditional parties in Slovakia contrasted with the framework parties offers an intriguing space to examine the significance and utilization of social organizations in their marketing and advancement. The principle objective of the commitment is to recognize the utilization of Facebook's social organization by political parties in Slovakia in the feeling of – extreme right versus situation party, with the accompanying point: recurrence and periodicity of posting, client movement on posts, keyword event and qualification of posts that serve to impart themes or advance Party. The incomplete objective distinguishes the substance of commitments posted on Facebook, recognize sort of posts used to advance the gathering or imparting political themes. Simultaneously, we are keen fair and

square of connection between clients in posts, while identifying the connection between post sharing, remarks, and likes. The outcomes show a generally adjusted proportion of post committed to conveying points and gathering advancement. The presence of a positive relationship between chosen variables taking all things together the cases has been affirmed. Lately a large number of political parties contending in this field have gone to utilizing marketing methods (Karbasforosha et al., 2019). That is the reason such terms as close to home marketing, political marketing and campaigns marketing are utilized meanwhile. This study intends to investigate the impact of political marketing blend on elector's expectation dependent on segment trademark in tenth parliament political decision in Tehran. As per limitless number of measurable populace, a sample comprising of 385 voters of tenth parliament political decision were chosen and examined by utilizing limitless factual populace recipe. Technique for the research depends on unmistakable survey research and is an applied study. The theoretical model is directed dependent on Political marketing blend which comprises of political item, political advancement, political spot, and political cost and segment factors including

sex, occupation, pay, instruction and age. The aftereffects of the research showed that every part of advancements, item, cost and area of the political marketing blend significantly affects voters' aims. Likewise, segment factors that were considered as an arbitrator variable showed that age and sex had no huge impact, while training, occupation and pay had a critical impact.

Conclusion

The literature on political marketing or marketing techniques used by political parties is quite scattered. Some focus on digital media marketing and social media marketing by the political parties is seen. While it deals with the marketing techniques used by political parties for winning votes, the recent literature is not so vocal about things like building a vote bank and developing voter loyalty. There is no doubt that marketing is inevitable for political parties. However, what kind of marketing channels apart from social media and platforms other than digital marketing does not appear to be researched much. It would be interesting to explore these relatively lesser researched areas so that an interesting application of marketing techniques is brought to light to benefit both academia and marketing professionals..

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